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SYNTHESIS OF SILVER NANOCOPOSITE WITH EUDRAGIT RL 100 FOR THE DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

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Abstract

Vacuum deposited thin discontinuous silver films on Eudragit RL 100 (Eu) were produced. Eudragit RL100 is insoluble in water at physiological pH values and capable of swelling, so they are good for the dispersion of active compounds. This polymer is being used for the enteric coating of tablets and for preparing controlled-release formulations. Hence, deposition of silver nano cluster on Eu would be useful for drug delivery system. The unique properties of silver nano particles (Ag NP) have been exploited within the fields of photonics and biotechnology over last decade due to their wide range of novel uses and application. The optical and plasmonic response of Ag NP onto thin layers of Eu shows encapsulation of nano particles. These nanoparticles exhibit unique optical properties originating from the characteristic surface plasmon by the collective motion of conduction electrons. Thus, the formation of silver nanoparticles was confirmed by UV/VIS absorption spectrum of nano polymer composite films.

Keywords: NANOPARTICLES; POLYMER BLENDS; THIN FILMS; VAPOR DEPOSITION; OPTICAL PROPERTIES.

INTRODUCTION

Polymer nanocomposites have been of great interest in recent years. Incorporating silver nanoparticle into a polymer matrix is more interesting because the resulting nanocomposites exhibit applications in catalysis, drug delivery, wound dressing and antimicrobial activity (Ivana D., 2014, Hatijah B., 2011).

Eudragit® RL 100 is copolymers of acrylic and methacrylic acid esters with a low content in quaternary ammonium groups. The ammonium groups are present as salts and make the polymers permeable. RL are copolymers of poly (ethylacrylate, methyl-methacrylate and chlorotrimethyl-ammonioethyl methacrylate), containing an amount of quaternary ammonium groups ranging between 8.8% and 12%. Silver ions being bioactive killed bacteria on infected wounds on living tissue and led

physician to use wound dressing containing silver sulfadiazine and Ag NP to treat external infections. Silver lining food helps in treating various remedies and ailments. Therefore, deposition of silver nano cluster on EU will be interesting as silver nano eudragit composite may find application in drug delivery system. The development of different approaches to control size and shape of silver nanoparticles enabled more efficient application of silver as antimicrobial agent. Tailoring of silver clusters can be achieved by modifying the polymer matrix by irradiation and doping.

One of the simplest and eco friendly techniques to form such particulate structures, which are generally known as island or discontinuous metal films, is through vacuum evaporation of metal on to a dielectric substrate by stopping the deposition at a very early stage. The temporal instability exhibited by island films even in vacuum is attributed to mobility of islands followed by coalescence (Wang, 2006). Further, these films get oxidized when they are exposed to atmosphere. The oxidation of islands causes an irreversible increase in electrical resistance (Bronstein, 2004). An interesting sub-surface particulate structure formation was reported when certain inorganic materials are deposited on to softened polymer substrates (Wang 2007, Kunz 1992, Rao 1999, Rao 2001). The morphology and formation of such structures depend on thermodynamic as well as deposition parameters (Rao 2001, Rao 1999, Parashar 2012). The use of softened polymère substrats provides the unique possibility of easily controlling the viscosity of the substrate to form a subsurface discontinuous silver particulate films.

EXPERIMENTAL

Eudragit ® RL 100 and (3-mercaptopropyl) trimethoxysilane (MPTMS) used in this study were procured from Röhm GmbH & Co. KG, Darmstadt, Germany and Sigma-Aldrich Chemicals Pvt. Ltd. The average molecular weight of Eu is approx. 150,000. The structure of Eu is as follows:

R₁ = H, CH₃

R₂ = CH₃, C₂H₅

Polymer films were prepared through solution casting by dissolving Eudrgjit in benzene.

Optical absorption spectra of the silver particulate films were obtained on a Shimadzu Uv-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer model SHIMADZU UV 3101 PC.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Silver nanocomposite film exhibits characteristic UV absorbance spectrum at a wavelength of 430 nm, due to the surface plasmon resonance of nanosized silver (Heilmann 1999, Fritzsche 1998, Akamatsu 2000, Carotenuto 2001). These nanoparticles exhibit unique optical properties originating from the characteristic surface plasmon by the collective motion of conduction electrons (Akamatsu 2000,

Carotenuto 2001). Thus, the formation of silver nanoparticles can also be confirmed by UV/VIS absorption spectrum of composite films (Kim 2003).

Spectral position, half width and intensity of the plasmon resonance strongly depend on the particle size, shape and the dielectric properties of the particle material and the surrounding medium (Heilmann 1998). Thus, the type of metal and the surrounding dielectric medium play a significant role in the excitation of particle plasmon resonance (PPR). The sensitivity of PPR frequency to small variations of these parameters can be exploited in various applications (Takele 2006). The differences in dispersion, size distribution and impregnation depth results from the differing natures of the polymeric hosts (Hassell 2006).

Figure 1: Optical absorption spectra for 150 nm silver particulate films deposited on Pure Eu and its blends.

Fig. 1 shows the optical absorption spectra recorded for 150 nm silver films deposited on polymeric blends of Eu held at 457 K at the deposition rate of 0.4 nm/s. For silver particles embedded in Eu blends, a shift of the resonance position to higher wavelength (red shift) were found for irradiated Eu (494 nm), Eu (+ 2.5 MPTMS) (429 nm) and negligible blue shift for Eu (+0.5MPTMS). These changes were correlated with changes of particle sizes and inter-separation in silver clusters. It is clearly seen (Fig.) that the plasmon resonance peak shifts towards the longer wavelength side as compared to pure eudragit (421 nm). Also, there is increase in intensity of absorbing peaks which signify the decrease of particles size (Kim 2003). Irradiation on Eu released free radicals which interact with silver clusters resulting decrease in size. Also, doping with 2.5 MPTMS is resulted decrease in size of silver clusters.

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